

Land Use Transformations Project (JHI-C3-1)

Milestone 22 – Farm Types and Rotations

Internal Report

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1 Introduction

Farm types and rotations data are key elements of the analysis within the [Land Use Transformations project](#).

Farm types are the main way in which data has been presented to SG and other stakeholders and is the way in which within agricultural sectors effects are identified and presented. Farm types are also a key way in which it is possible to define land use change (LUC) scenarios – see milestone M21, where dairy farms are preserved from undergoing tree planting. This scenario defining can be either representing theoretical or empirically based definition of how likely changes are likely to occur (e.g. high value dairy land is less likely to see trees planted) or may be a normative part of the scenario outcomes ought (no loss of local capacity for productions such as dairy). More robust and sophisticated ways to define farm types have been explored to try and improve coverage and deal with land holdings and phenomena that are challenging to include in agricultural classifications.

Rotations are an important element in defining the extent and intensity of agricultural land use, with some suspicion that for substantial areas of Scotland there is little evidence of rotation being implemented at all (at least as reported via IACS land use claims). Taking a multi-temporal view of land cover/use is also of value in identifying relationships with land capability and the extent of crop based (arable) land uses (where modelling e.g. of spring barley yields should take place).

2 Data sources

Farm type data comes from the financial (standard outputs) based analysis by the June Agricultural census team (for years 2012 to 2023) and is available at holding and business level. Holding level analysis is generally to be preferred as this preserves information on the range of land managements undertaken not just the dominant financial model e.g. where business has horticulture and upland enterprises then at business level the upland become visible only as anomalous “extra” area. This data is supplemented by the MP2 Address List which is a dataset maintained by AgCensus team with contact information (not used here) and with holding classifications added.

The land cover data for the rotations analysis comes from the IACS-LPIS annual Single Application Form (SAF) returns. The data used in the rotation analysis is for the years 2016 to 2022. These are standardised data from the FUTURES system in RPID. Data for 2015 are also available but this was the first year of FUTURES operation and also a transition year for the research team in their use of the data. Data quality issues means data for 2015 is less reliable but could be integrated at a later date. Earlier years of IACS-LPIS have also been used in previous policy led analyses (2005 - 2014) but these came from the earlier RPID IT system and in a different format and have not been quality controlled in the same way as the later datasets. The option to look back further to add to the rotations (land use change) data is being considered (March 2024).

All the data above is managed under Data Sharing Agreement 48.

3 Methods

The farm types analysis has combined the JAC and MP2-AL data (reported here). The mapping of the farm types is described further in Milestone 21 and in the Farm Type story map.

The processing of the 2016-22 IACS-LPIS data is presented in detail in [this github code repository](#) but essentially has the following stages each of which deals with data quality issues as defined below.

1. Import and Pseudonymise data into database.

2. Line up seasonal sheet records with permanent sheet records.
3. Correct seasonal and permanent records as required when they do not match.
4. Correct commons claims against commons fields where the commons claims are larger than the commons area.
5. Attach to spatial information from LPIS, connecting claims to fields from Jan in the next year, then going back through previous years' field snapshots until no further linkages are possible.
6. Check for and correct overlaps of greater than 10 ha where claims are against fields that occupy the same space.
7. Export as a final dataset into the database.

For this analysis, the predominant land use is selected using an algorithm that combines land uses and selects the largest per field.

The rotations data has at this point been generated from six rasterised maps¹ of predominant land use combined into "keys" made use of the six crop code names and presented as tables and other visualisations.

4 Results

4.1 Farm types

Combining the ComboFarm type² with the MP2 types give the following results – see Table 1 and Table 2.

The tables are colour coded to show where additional information on farm types can be derived. The key lines are for Non-Classified, No Farm Type and not in JAC (shown in the dark green). For these cases the MP2 type can provide type information for 3,892 of 11,229 holdings, mostly common grazings or forestry businesses. This is particularly useful when considering rural payments analysis where the lack of farm types for some SIACS businesses can generate uncertainty. Where there is no JAC holding recorded but there is data in the MP2 list these holdings may not be submitting a JAC return as they are forestry only holdings (1,648) and MP2 is the only source of type data. That other apparently agricultural holdings have no matching JAC record is potentially due to turnover of holdings but the issues with making matches have been persistent and may be worth more detailed examination.

Note that the area figures presented in Table 2 use the JAC total area per holding so there is no data (yellow) for the not in JAC types, but also that the areas of common grazings and forestry are not correct – e.g. 327 ha for 1,055 forestry holdings and no data for common grazings (since this is not recorded in the JAC). Other sources of area data are readily available for SIACS businesses, but these limitations are more serious for the beyond SIACS population.

For the 301 holdings referred to a SIACS Main/Minor or the 6,368 just classed as Main/Minor without type (highlighted in yellow) the lack of farm type data still presents a limitation, though mainly for non SIACS holdings which limits the impact on payments analysis. Again, the reasons for the lack of JAC farm types are likely holding turnover.

¹ Rasterised maps are used as otherwise the analysis has to cope with minor field boundary alignments generating spurious artefacts.

² The ComboFarm type is derived by the Hutton team from types High, Med and Low and Robust to give a classification seen as useful for policy development purposes in a variety of farm payment scenario analyses.

Table 1: Cross tabulation of ComboFarmType and MP2 classes – count of holding

Count of Holdings	MP2 Types										In JAC not	
	SIACS Main	SIACS Minor	Main	Minor	Large Poultry Unit	Sheep Stock Club	C/Grazings	Forestry	Forestry Composite	in MP2	All Holdings	
Specialist Horticulture and Permanent Cropping	173	23	420	360	12					8	996	
General Field Cropping	1,281	13	214	243	18					36	1,805	
Specialist cereals, oilseeds and protein crops	1,606	22	455	180	18					75	2,356	
Mixed Crops - Livestock	1,149	24	187	252	24					16	1,652	
Specialist granivores	105	35	251	693	147					14	1,245	
Various granivores combined	32	10	58	132	6					4	242	
Specialist dairying	931	1	64	12	9					3	1,020	
Specialist cattle - rearing and fattening	3,996	135	610	295	25				1	34	5,096	
Sheep and cattle combined	1,251	20	131	38	3	1				6	1,450	
Specialist sheep and Goats	2,531	855	1,689	2,419	23	37	1		3	113	7,671	
Various grazing livestock	762	204	1,181	3,113	22	2				42	5,326	
Graziers	1,861	1,101	3,485	12,878	38			2	36	335	19,736	
Non Classified	22	59	165	1,262	27	1			9	17	1,562	
In JAC but no Farm Type	65	137	2,280	1,485	10		1,123	1,055	7	651	6,813	
In MP2 not in JAC	9	9	1,065	111	2		8	1,648	2		2,854	
All Holdings	15,774	2,648	12,255	23,473	384	41	1,132	2,705	58	1,354	59,824	

Table 2: Cross tabulation of ComboFarmType and MP2 classes – JAC area of holding

JAC Area (ha)	MP2 Types										In JAC not	
	SIACS Main	SIACS Minor	Main	Minor	Large Poultry Unit	Sheep Stock Club	C/Grazings	Forestry	Forestry Composite	in MP2	All Holdings	
Specialist Horticulture and Permanent Cropping	35,167	194	8,571	1,262	198					1,744	47,136	
General Field Cropping	245,726	78	12,453	801	2,992					4,005	266,055	
Specialist cereals, oilseeds and protein crops	215,569	121	17,919	2,124	1,814					4,750	242,296	
Mixed Crops - Livestock	245,293	126	6,273	917	3,512					1,347	257,467	
Specialist granivores	15,052	287	2,272	2,846	6,402					410	27,269	
Various granivores combined	8,540	46	591	498	468					7	10,151	
Specialist dairying	150,001	1	4,374	107	1,323					291	156,097	
Specialist cattle - rearing and fattening	828,886	1,140	45,761	3,582	9,658				617	3,455	893,098	
Sheep and cattle combined	679,128	154	12,462	420	1,850	0				3,901	697,914	
Specialist sheep and Goats	1,161,870	10,142	96,077	22,159	13,368	25,599	84		3,653	21,898	1,354,851	
Various grazing livestock	252,151	2,350	65,006	23,531	5,421	3,400				2,451	354,310	
Graziers	737,884	41,295	343,614	220,853	1,227			201	13,623	14,808	1,373,505	
Non Classified	8,046	5,031	5,456	14,088	48	90			309	401	33,469	
In JAC but no Farm Type	2,887	2,778	38,042	12,675	12			372	581	2,469	59,817	
In MP2 not in JAC												
All Holdings	4,586,200	63,742	658,869	305,861	48,295	29,089	84	572	18,783	61,937	5,773,434	

For the other lines in the table the MP2 data can provide useful additional information. The large poultry unit type (light green) could potentially indicate significant secondary activity (for non-granivore businesses). How significant the information is likely depends on the definition of large (currently unknown to the team but given the small numbers of holdings (381) it is possible that these are the largest units in Scotland). That they are spread across all Combo types does though raise a question on whether this is the case as the expectation might be that the largest units in Scotland would be in the specialist or combined granivore types.

Sheep stock clubs and common grazings (mid green) are valuable types given their differences in tenure – though it would be good to check if such holdings can contain other stock types with small numbers classified as types other than specialist sheep holdings (light orange).

There are a small number of cases (42) where there seems to be a discrepancy between the MP2 type and the JAC (highlighted in orange), mainly for forestry or forestry composite that could be expected to be Unclassified or no Farm Type. The forestry composite may, depending on definition, contain some grazing land, perhaps not used by the holding, and thus the grazier definition would be correct with the forestry composite type being useful extra data.

4.2 Farm type mapping

The JAC farm types have been mapped in as part of the [Story Map](#) (Deliverable D3 of the [Land Use Transformation](#) project). This illustrates the issues and distributions of farm types outlined above.

4.3 Rotations

The rotations data is complete but only subjected to limited descriptive analysis, see Table 3. There are 99,305 unique combinations of crop codes present across the period 2016-21. For some of these

classes there are technical changes in how land use is defined that have occurred and unifying these where appropriate will cut the number combinations. The unique combinations to date have preserved the temporal ordering of the crop codes as this can provide useful information where there are either changes in definitions or reasons to see changes in declarations in response to regulatory reform (past cases have seen changes between PGRS and RGR of this type). In some cases, the data of a change is not significant, and equivalences of unique combinations can be combined – e.g. for combinations of TGRS and PGRS. Further analysis will begin to generate the useful equivalences both temporal variations and where individual crop codes may be combined (e.g. cereals or spring cereals etc).

Table 3: Largest by area unique crop code combinations over the period 2016-21

Unique crop code combinations 2016-2021	Area (ha over 6 years)	Share of all area
RGR->RGR->RGR->RGR->RGR->RGR	268,679,324	51.5%
PGRS->PGRS->PGRS->PGRS->PGRS->PGRS	83,392,845	16.0%
EXCL->EXCL->EXCL->EXCL->EXCL->EXCL	42,556,349	8.2%
SB->SB->SB->SB->SB->SB	5,940,677	1.1%
TGRS->TGRS->TGRS->TGRS->PGRS->PGRS	4,497,786	0.9%
RGR->RGR->RGR->RGR->RGR->EXCL	3,846,771	0.7%
RGR->RGR->RGR->RGR->EXCL->EXCL	2,885,137	0.6%
EXCL->EXCL->RGR->RGR->RGR->RGR	2,613,597	0.5%
TGRS->TGRS->PGRS->PGRS->PGRS->PGRS	2,094,114	0.4%
TGRS->TGRS->TGRS->TGRS->TGRS->PGRS	2,038,155	0.4%
TGRS->PGRS->PGRS->PGRS->PGRS->PGRS	1,930,475	0.4%
TREE->TREE->TREE->TREE->TREE->TREE	1,797,288	0.3%
RGR->RGR->RGR->RGR->RGR->NETR_NA	1,585,071	0.3%
WDG->WDG->WDG->WDG->WDG->WDG	1,561,439	0.3%
TREE->EXCL->EXCL->EXCL->EXCL->EXCL	1,504,217	0.3%
RGR->EXCL->EXCL->EXCL->EXCL->EXCL	1,366,304	0.3%
PGRS->RGR->PGRS->PGRS->RGR->RGR	1,236,095	0.2%
EXCL->EXCL->EXCL->EXCL->RGR->EXCL	1,207,449	0.2%
SB->SB->SB->SB->TGRS->TGRS	972,230	0.2%
SB->TGRS->TGRS->TGRS->TGRS->TGRS	967,446	0.2%
NETR_NA->NETR_NA->NETR_NA->NETR_NA->NETR_NA->NETR_NA	955,180	0.2%
SB->SB->TGRS->TGRS->TGRS->TGRS	838,736	0.2%
RGR->RGR->RGR->RGR->NETR_NA->NETR_NA	793,773	0.2%
PGRS->PGRS->PGRS->PGRS->SB->SB	781,735	0.1%
RGR->RGR->RGR->RGR->RGR->PGRS	777,290	0.1%
RGR->RGR->RGR->RGR->PGRS->PGRS	763,882	0.1%
EXCL->EXCL->EXCL->EXCL->RGR->RGR	697,591	0.1%
PGRS->PGRS->PGRS->PGRS->TGRS->TGRS	689,596	0.1%
EXCL->RGR->RGR->RGR->RGR->RGR	584,326	0.1%
RGR->PGRS->PGRS->PGRS->PGRS->PGRS	553,983	0.1%
EXCL->RGR->RGR->RGR->EXCL->EXCL	548,054	0.1%
PGRS->PGRS->PGRS->PGRS->PGRS->SB	534,794	0.1%
PGRS->PGRS->PGRS->PGRS->RGR->RGR	529,829	0.1%
RGR->RGR->PGRS->PGRS->PGRS->PGRS	517,068	0.1%

The table highlights the largest crop code combinations. The colour codes use are as follows:

1. Pink are combinations with either continuing RGR (rough grazing) or rough grazing changing to PGRS (permanent grassland). Continuing RGR is the largest combination at 51.5% but RGR sees many transitions – some permanent to forestry, some definitional (exclusions) and others based on interpretations e.g. between RGR and PGRS.

2. PGRS dominated combinations are shown in blue and there are transitions here from PGRS to TGRS (temporary grassland) and arable crops (mainly spring barley – highlighted in orange).
3. Exclusions shown in grey are those areas of farms on which payments are not made. They are a diversity of covers and habitats and can be extensive and unchanging (8.2% of area over the six years). Such areas may become more significant if their management or enhancement become part of the Tier 2 Enhanced Conditionality payments regime.
4. Arable bases combinations (in orange) include mainly spring barley (the monoculture is just under 6M ha over the six years), or spring barley combined with temporary grass. It is possible to distinguish where spring barley is present in most years (with grass as a break crop) and others where spring barley is a more infrequent crop (likely part of livestock systems).
5. Several forms of woodlands can be seen (highlighted in green) either as continuing cover or as change in cover (typically from RGR). New trees (NETR_NA) are distinguished since these may still be included in claims for area-based payments. Grant aided forestry is highlighted as woodland grant (WDG) but how reliable a difference from those recorded as TREE is unknown.

Options for quantifying and mapping patterns of land use change and their linkage with Farm Types will be undertaken in Year 3 of the project. The rotation data set will also be used to identify and define areas that may be vulnerable of climate change by mapping the range of locations in which such crops have occurred.

5 Farm type issues to be addressed

5.1 Lack of farm type coverage

The version of the farm types mapping deployed for the LUC analysis has a coverage of 65% of land area though this is an overestimate since the coverage area includes overlaps. While all holdings and businesses should have a farm type defined the has been an ongoing challenge in assigning farm types since the start of farm-type-based analyses (2008). Previously this has always been assumed to be a combination of broken links due to business/holding change or limitations on the FID-holding-business linkage data held by the Hutton team. Options for using the FID to Holding relationships present in the LPIS data have been explored in the Land Reform Project JHI-E3-1) in conducting the support for the Land Reform Bill BR1A. In the past these relationships were not considered reliable compared to those within IACS itself but the option to test such data as a way for extending the reach of the farm types classification will be explored.

There has also been suspicion that the population of land management entities may have within it examples that cannot fit well with conventional agriculturally defined types (e.g. woodland only holdings). Preliminary testing with the types contained within the MP2 Address List (MP2-AL) has demonstrated that this is effective in extending the coverage considerably and adding other insights (such as identifying Sheep Stock Clubs etc). How to combine the MP2-AL with the Combo farm types is not always straight forward depending on analysis purposes so a method that both combines and preserves the separate information will likely be needed.

5.2 Overlaps of farm types

Where there is more than one user of land within a parcel then different farm types can overlap (at least cartographically if the whole parcel is used). In the claim by claim based analysis typically

undertaken in, for example agricultural payment analysis, then the areas (land use, claimed or paid etc) are preserved and the integrity of the financial analysis maintained. These areas can also be recorded for the farm types present but it is harder to devise meaningful ways in which different farm types can be combined (the totals or rates for financial analyses not being appropriate. For the LUC analysis the overlaps where multiple farm types are present have not yet been eliminated and as a consequence the areas per farm type are overestimated.

Options for eliminating the overlaps could make use of secondary mapping where this can differentiate on the basis of land cover (e.g. between a business claiming crop A and another with crop B). Such differentiation is though not simple to devise and implement but options of looking at exclusions and rotations data may be helpful as well as adding woodlands data from NFI as has been done for other LU/LUC based analyses.

5.3 Cartographical compromises in mapping farm types

As a by-product of the overlap there can also be cartographical compromises in multi-user polygons as only one farm type per polygon can be shown (unless mixed classes are used, and this can become very complex in an already multi-category mapping). This is particularly noticeable when individual farm types are mapped and changing between the maps highlights where farm types “flip” between values. Disaggregating as noted above will help with cartographical challenges but other options may also help (see next section).

5.4 Commons and other farm type options

The most visible examples of the farm-type flipping can be seen in crofting counties where the whole polygon associated with the common is linked to each holding and a diversity of farm types are present. The diversity is an outcome of the very low standard outputs values for the large areas of rough grazing in the commons, and the low numbers of stock present. This means that any diversified activity such as horticultural crops or granivores/dairy cattle present tip the holding into one of these types despite the small areas devoted to such activities (typically on the in-bye). The differentiation in the farm type mapping with a commons area is highly undesirable as stock are free to roam. One option to reduce overlaps and flipping is to treat the commons separately as their own farm type. This would mean that a holding could then have a sensible representation of the area linked to diversified activities (small) yet still be linked to commons for either crofting focused analysis or to differentiate within other farm types as needed.

5.5 More farm types?

Other supplementary datasets could also be used to supplement farm type definitions – especially where they are not principally agriculture. Examples would include active muirburn and grouse butts as a way of differentiation within rough grazing land cover – driven grouse.

For multi-holding businesses it may also be more informative to maintain the granularity of per holding types and for businesses to potentially have a list rather than a single type so that the populations affected by any sector specific issue can be identified.